

EMPOWERMENT OF AIR DEFENSE AREA IN MILITARY OPERATIONS OTHER THAN WAR (CASE STUDY OF INDONESIA AIR FORCE SUPPORT IN HANDLING TERRORISM)

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Abstract

In accordance with Indonesian legislation, the military plays a justified role in counterterrorism efforts. This qualitative study explores the empowerment of air defense areas within the framework of Military Operations Other Than War (MOOTW), focusing on the support provided by the Indonesian Air Force in addressing terrorism. Data for this research were gathered through interviews and observations, employing a purposive technique to select informants with a comprehensive understanding of the Indonesian Air Force's involvement in counterterrorism. Data triangulation was used for validation. The findings reveal that the Indonesian Air Force, through dedicated agencies, engages in various activities, including direct community guidance, seminar-based socialization, and community outreach services. This study contributes critical insights to national security studies, specifically enhancing the understanding of air defense area empowerment in the context of MOOTW, particularly concerning counterterrorism efforts. Notably, this research fills a gap in existing literature by providing a comprehensive examination of air defense area empowerment in MOOTW, with a specific focus on the Indonesian Air Force's role in countering terrorism.

Introduction:

In contemporary security discourse, the focus has expanded beyond traditional military threats to encompass non-military challenges, prompting crucial considerations around the concept of "security for whom?" This perspective underscores the integral link between human security and state security, emphasizing the state's responsibility to safeguard its citizens (Al A'raf, 2015; Luckham & Kirk, 2013). Within this modern security paradigm, the interdependence of human security and state security becomes apparent.

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Among the non-traditional security concerns, the rise and evolution of terrorist movements pose significant challenges to human security. Terrorist groups, driven by political motives, often target innocent civilians to achieve their objectives, posing a direct threat to human security (Callaway & Harrelson-Stephens, 2006; Laqueur, 1987). The beginning of the 21st century witnessed a series of terrorist incidents in Indonesia, including bombings, attacks on churches, and other public spaces, resulting in considerable casualties (Nasrum, 2016; Evanalia, 2017).

To counteract such threats, the Indonesian government, in accordance with legislative provisions (UU No. 34 of 2004 and UU no. 5 of 2018), involves the military, specifically the Indonesian Air Force (TNI AU), in Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP) to address acts of terrorism. Recognizing the continued threat of terrorism, the government utilizes various institutions, including the Indonesian Air Force, to counteract both ideological and separatist motives associated with terrorism.

This study delves into the empowerment of air defense areas within the framework of OMSP, with a specific focus on the support provided by the Indonesian Air Force in addressing terrorism. Despite existing studies on coordination between local governments and the Army in empowering defense areas and examinations of marine defense areas, there is a gap regarding the specific analysis of air defense area empowerment, particularly in the context of counterterrorism efforts (Armawi, 2011; Jati, 2017; Mariana, 2006; Adnyana, 2017; Asmani, 2014).

The objective of this research is to comprehensively analyze the empowerment of air defense areas in the context of OMSP, emphasizing the Indonesian Air Force's role in combating terrorism. This study contends that, given the persistent threat of terrorism, there is a critical need to explore the effectiveness of the Indonesian Air Force's involvement and potential strategies in countering this multifaceted challenge.

The subsequent sections of this paper include a Literature Review, detailing relevant studies on national defense, air defense, and OMSP in the context of terrorism. Following that, the Research Methodology section outlines the approach adopted for this study. The Results section discusses the findings, and the paper concludes with a summary of key insights.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to identify and analyze the empowerment of the air defense area in dealing with terrorism.

LITERATURE REVIEW

National Defense in the Threat of Terrorism

According to Myers, as quoted by Tulak, Kraft, and Silbaugh (2003), defense is the protection of territory, sovereignty, domestic population, and important infrastructure against external threats and aggression. If the state determines the war against terrorism, the approach taken by the state is no longer based on only one approach, namely the security approach, but also on the defense approach. The war against terrorism, like the war against ISIS, is an asymmetric war in which, in this war model, there is always room for military involvement. The military's involvement in the war against terrorism is carried out because terror organizations are considered no longer just committing criminal acts or violating ordinary laws. They are also considered a threat to the existence of the state (Mukhtar, 2016; Triskaputri, 2019).

In the past, the national defense could be seen from the use of the armed forces to protect the national territory from the invasion of other countries, and defense was seen as an act of war that attacked other countries. However, at present, the tendency is that the current defense factor is more focused on managing national defense, which includes guarding against all potential attacks from other countries and threats of violence that arise from within, such as rebellions separatist movements (Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces, 2015).

Air Defense

In the past and present, air defense systems have been designed to efficiently provide strategic warning of potential threats, and especially after the start of a battle (Gapinski, Krzysztofik, & Koruba', 2018). As for in peacetime, air defense systems are used to monitor airspace, identify, and when necessary, to intercept and destroy something that is considered a nuisance. The power of air defense systems has become an important part of the overall defense system; even the best defenses sometimes fail to carry out missions in peacetime because they are not adequately equipped with strategic attack warnings (Evans, 2005).

According to Rosier (1967), although it cannot determine the victory of the war itself, an efficient air defense system can provide hope and become an early warning system against enemy attacks from the air. Air defense can complement the defense force (Ormrod & Turnbull, 2016); effective air defense can help avoid greater troop losses or as a deterrence effect. Furthermore, Rosier (1967) also emphasizes that at least the air defense system provides five basic needs, including early warning, tracking, identification, ability to intercept and destroy.

Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP)

Military involvement in dealing with terrorism, also known as counter-terrorism activities, has been carried out in many countries; military activities in counter-terrorism are part of Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP) (Ashari, 2020; Jogerst, 2005). The military's involvement in handling terrorism is expected to strengthen the national security system comprehensively and not partially because the involvement of the military in OMSP will encourage synergy between national security actors or other related institutions (Darwanto, 2015).

Although the military can be involved by civilian government authorities to carry out OMSP, in OMSP operations, the military remains with established war doctrines and principles. The principles of war applied in OMSP include objective, business unity, legitimacy, perseverance, restraint, and security (Dougherty, 2012). For the deployment of military air power during OMSP, especially for handling peacekeeping operations, the Air Force is required to carry out air patrols within the operating zone. Air patrols are useful for controlling airspace and assisting ground patrols, such as denying other flights to enter the operating zone, denying forces that deliberately want to enter the operating zone, and preventing surprise attacks (Vick, Orletsky, Shulsky, & Stillion, 1997).

METHODOLOGY

This study aims to describe and analyze the empowerment of air defense areas in OMSP, especially in case studies of the support of the Indonesian Air Force in handling terrorism. By referring to what is being researched, the design of this research uses qualitative methods.

In this study, the data in the field were then collected using various techniques or methods, such as through interviews, observation, and documentation. The technique was chosen to provide convenience in research activities and was not intended to limit the level of flexibility of the researcher as an instrument in the field.

Interviews were conducted on informants who became the object of this research using purposive techniques. Observations were made on various activities used as research subjects, namely activities in the form of air defense area empowerment activities in OMSP, especially in terms of support from the Indonesian Air Force in handling terrorism. Meanwhile, documentation analysis was carried out on various documents related to the empowerment of the air defense area in OMSP, which mainly deals with the handling of terrorism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Handling Terrorism by the Indonesian Air Force

The involvement of the Indonesian Air Force in dealing with terrorism issues is based on the development and level of threat from terrorism, where terrorism is categorized as a form of extraordinary crime because the impact

of the crime it causes is also categorized as extraordinary (Nasution, 2018; Rahman, 2020). Because terrorism that occurs has its characteristics or peculiarities, plus terrorism activities that also occur in Indonesia have a fairly high level of threat to national security conditions, the handling of terrorism also requires extraordinary measures (Hatta, 2019).

To deal with terrorism, the Indonesian Air Force established Satbravo-90, as one of the Special Forces, Satbravo-90 with the specifications of its expertise that can be used in counter-terrorism operations with confidence that its success cannot be doubted. In carrying out its operations, the Satbravo-90 can also move without an identity. With the increasingly incessant war on terror in the world, where terrorist actors also have a capable ability to carry out attacks on vital or strategic objects, the Indonesian Air Force can intercept terrorists, especially those carrying weapons. Including Indonesia, special forces from the military have been used in operations to free hostages, including those that can be used if terrorists attack the country (Wulansari, 2017).

Air Defense Area Empowerment

The implementation of the empowerment of the air defense area is one of the duties or responsibilities of the Indonesian Air Force as a means of state defense from the air dimension. The task of empowering air defense areas by the Indonesian Air Force is not only carried out for the benefit of state defense but also assists the government in creating a conducive atmosphere or even prospering the community (Dispenau, 2017; Hakim, 2021). Based on this, it is possible to empower the air defense area to carry out the tasks of Military Operations Other than War (OMSP) in the context of national defense.

In overcoming threats to national security, the empowerment of air defense areas can be aimed at airspace resilience and affect the surrounding community among the empowerment of air defense that can have positive implications or contributions to the community, namely the involvement of units or the use of the Indonesian Air Force base to guide the surrounding community, such as through aerospace sports activities, as well as the Saka Dirgantara Scouts. With this condition, the community will automatically support the existence of the Indonesian Air Force base in increasing regional resilience (Yufrinal, 2008).

DISCUSSION

Analysis of Empowerment of Air Defense Areas in Handling Terrorism

Planning: The stages of realizing the empowerment of defense areas are also generally carried out through the following stages:

- a. **Assessment Stage:** Conducted by analyzing strategic environmental conditions to identify the potential of regional, national resources, anticipating various forms of threats to state sovereignty, and assisting in the formulation of the components of national defense.
- b. **Inventory Stage:** This stage is carried out by collecting and managing data on national resource potential, which includes the type, quantity, location, and production capability, and economic value. In addition, this stage also seeks to see the obstacles in increasing the strength of the national defense component. This stage aims to record the potential of national resources as components that can be fostered to become components of support in national defense.
- c. **Standardization Stage.** This stage is carried out by mapping the potential of national resources and taking into account national standards and Indonesian military standards to be upgraded to become a force that supports national defense.
- d. **Recruitment Stage.** After standardization has been carried out on all potential national resources as a component of supporting national defense, then the determination and determination of national resources that can be fostered into a component strength of the national defense force is carried out.

e. Development Stage. This stage is carried out by managing all kinds of national resources that have been selected to be the main, reserve, and supporting components.

f. Usage Stage. The strength that has been selected will then be used through a national defense strategy, both military and non-military strategies, with the aim of national defense.

Other efforts related to planning in dealing with the threat of terrorism are also carried out by forming an agency unit. The command formed to handle special operations such as terrorism is the Special Operations Command (Koopsus TNI). The quantity, quality, and complexity of the threat of terrorism are still strong, and its network is increasingly spreading in the community. Therefore, the need for the Koopsus TNI is very important to increase strength in dealing with the threat of terrorism.

Coaching: In the implementation of the development of air defense areas, the Indonesian Air Force participates has an obligation to empower the air defense and state defense areas, including:

First, Development of Aerospace Potential (Binpotdirga). Spotdirga carried out this Binpotdirga as an effort by the Indonesian Air Force to assist the government in carrying out state defense and prospering the community while creating a conducive atmosphere. This event was conducted in the format of aerospace sports and the Saka Scouts meeting. This potential is one of the targets of the Indonesian Air Force to be fostered and empowered to become part of the component of national defense.

Second, the Development of Aerospace Social Communication (Komsosdirga). This agenda is carried out in various forms such as seminars, workshops, or other social communication activities such as meeting visits to agencies outside the Air Force. Activities such as holding national seminars aim to carry out the duties of the Indonesian Air Force in empowering the air defense area (AU Dispense, 2020).

Third, Karya Bhakti. This activity is carried out by carrying out community service and service operations independently and with other agencies. The activities carried out in Karya Bhakti are conducting joint activities with the sustainable community. This is done to increase the closeness between the Indonesian Air Force and the community. In addition, this effort is also carried out to provide a sense of security for the community, especially from the threat of terrorism (Sut, 2020).

Development of direction and control: Development of direction and control as the third indicator concerns the ability of local units to develop and control programs related to preventing terrorism, including community involvement in creating environmental security and building public awareness of the potential threats from terrorism, together with the community in controlling environmental safety.

The development of the direction of developing air defense areas in overcoming the movement of terrorism can be categorized into two, namely violations of the national air defense area (terrorist acts that occur above the national airspace) and violations of regional air defense, namely violations that occur in the territorial area of the Indonesian Air Force. National airspace defense efforts can be carried out by deploying enforcement forces to deal with actions in the national airspace, both fighter aircraft and special capability personnel to deal with acts of terrorism on aircraft.

According to the results of interviews conducted with the Bravo 90 Paskhas Unit of the Indonesian Air Force, in their daily life, the Air Force continues to socialize the dangers and threats of terrorism to all soldiers, their families, and the surrounding community. The Air Force does not carry out terrorist countermeasures independently but synergizes and coordinates with related units and agencies and the government in handling terrorist acts that will occur. Suppose an act of terrorism occurs within the territory of national jurisdiction, such as a hijacking of a plane. In that case, the Indonesian Air Force can carry out the stages of interception to prosecution in accordance with applicable operating standards and based on orders from the top command.

Utilization of all national potential: This indicator is related to how prepared the military is in preparing all potential forces (local units) to be used in insurgency or armed attacks. Based on interviews conducted with informants from the Bravo 90 Paskhas Unit of the Indonesian Air Force that a unit has been formed to be then able to utilize the potential of resources more optimally, among them are:

a. Dispotdirga or the Office of Aerospace Potential is an organization of Indonesian Air Force staff that was formed with the main task of carrying out the development of national potential in the aerospace aspect, which includes the fields of Human Resources, Natural/Artificial Resources, and Aerospace Interests in the preparation of Reserve and Supporting Components. The development of the national potential above is expected to provide information and education for countering terrorism as part of OMSP.

b. Korpaskhas, or Special Forces Corps of the Indonesian Air Force, is a special force that has combat capabilities on land, sea, and air. Korpaskhas can deal with acts of terrorism with the existence of a special Anti-terror Elite Unit under its ranks, namely the Bravo 90 Paskhas Unit, which is tasked with cracking down on all acts of terrorism; that occur by the orders and policies of the top command.

CONCLUSION

Of the several threats included in Military Operations, acts of terrorism are a threat that until now there is an increase in network, military strength, and damage caused. Therefore, to suppress these threats, acts of terrorism are no longer only seen as ordinary criminal acts but are included in the category of extraordinary crimes. With the development of acts of terrorism that are a threat to the nation, the involvement of the Indonesian National Armed Forces is important to participate in counteracting the existence of terrorism. In line with the rules regarding the empowerment of defense areas in the face of threats, the Indonesian National Army needs to participate in empowering the region to maximize all kinds of potentials possessed by the state to counter the threat of terrorism.

In this case, planning efforts are carried out in the form of a division of plans and the steps taken to achieve the maximum level of empowerment of the defense area. To develop defense areas, the Indonesian Air Force, through the agency units that have been created, has carried out several types of activities ranging from direct guidance to the community, socialization through seminars. Also, activities were carried out by going directly to the community as a form of service and bringing the community closer with the Indonesian Air Force. Finally, to optimize the resources owned by the state to become a component of aid and a component of defense reserves against terrorism, the Indonesian Air Force established the Aerospace Potential Service and the Indonesian Air Force Special Forces Corps to carry out activities for empowering the defense area.

For the Indonesian Air Force, this research is expected to be material for consideration regarding the steps that need to be taken to support the implementation of OMSP, especially in dealing with terrorism. For the government, it is hoped that this research can provide a view on the need for participation in optimizing the role of the Indonesian Air Force through the empowerment of air defense areas for dealing with terrorism, but by still taking into account the applicable rules or regulations.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

It is hoped that there will be other research that can develop studies on the empowerment of air defense areas in military operations other than the war on case studies of Indonesian Air Force support in dealing with terrorism, with different theories or research methods so that they can add views or research analysis in security studies.

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